

ARTS

DISCUSSION ON THE MUSIC SELECTION LOGIC AND EMOTION-DIFFERENTIATED MUSIC APPLICATION MODEL OF FIVE-ELEMENT MUSIC BASED ON THE "TREATING EMOTION WITH EMOTION" THEORY

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Abstract

As a characteristic non-pharmacological therapy for regulating emotions in traditional Chinese medicine (TCM), five-element music therapy is mostly applied following the traditional zang-fu organ corresponding music selection mode in clinical practice. This conventional model has drawbacks such as prioritizing zang-fu organs over emotions, rigid music selection, and non-standardized music application, which restrict the core advantages of the "treating emotion with emotion" theory. Based on the classic theory of "treating emotion with emotion" in *Huangdi Neijing*, this paper sorts out the correspondence and compatibility relationships among five tones, five elements, and five emotions, analyzes the advantages and disadvantages of traditional music selection methods, and establishes the principle of emotion-restricting music selection. A refined music selection logic for five-emotion imbalance and a closed-loop emotion-differentiated music application model integrating identification, compatibility, implementation, and feedback are constructed. This paper also summarizes the existing problems and research limitations of current therapy application and prospects the optimization directions. This study effectively compensates for the shortcomings of traditional music application, improves the theoretical system of five-tone emotion regulation, and provides theoretical references and practical paradigms for the precise and standardized music therapy intervention of emotional imbalance disorders.

Keywords: treating emotion with emotion, five-element music, five-tone therapy, music selection logic, emotion-differentiated music application, emotional imbalance.

I. Core Theoretical Basis and Compatibility Mechanism

1.1 Connotation and Therapeutic Mechanism of the "Treating Emotion with Emotion" Theory

"Treating emotion with emotion" is a distinctive core therapeutic principle of TCM emotional medicine, which was first recorded in *Huangdi Neijing*. Derived from the five-element generation and restraint laws of TCM, it breaks through the traditional intervention mode of regulating zang-fu organs with drugs and initiates a non-pharmacological therapeutic approach of emotional restriction and balancing imbalance. *Suwen · Yin-Yang Corresponding to Manifestations* clearly establishes the core system of five emotions corresponding to five elements and mutual restraint of five emotions. It categorizes human emotional activities into anger, joy, thinking, sorrow, and fear, which correspond to wood, fire, earth, metal, and water respectively, forming a fixed mutual restraint relationship: anger restrains thinking, thinking restrains fear, fear restrains joy, joy restrains sorrow, and sorrow restrains anger. This provides a core theoretical basis for the treatment of emotional disorders.

TCM theory holds that human emotional activities originate from the movement of zang-fu organ qi mechanism. Normal emotional expression can harmonize zang-fu organs, smooth qi movement, and maintain the balance of yin and yang in the body. Excessive, persistent stagnant or disordered emotions will disrupt the steady state of zang-fu qi movement, leading to abnormal ascent and descent of qi, disharmony of zang-fu qi and blood, and further inducing physical and mental diseases. Different emotional imbalances cause specific

disorders of qi movement: anger leads to upward qi movement, joy leads to sluggish qi movement, overthinking leads to qi stagnation, sorrow leads to qi depression, and fear leads to downward qi movement. The core therapeutic mechanism of "treating emotion with emotion" is to use the five-element restraint law to restrain and relieve excessive and abnormal emotions with moderate and peaceful emotions, correct qi disorder through emotional intervention, calm the imbalance of zang-fu organs, and ultimately achieve the therapeutic goal of "treating diseases to obtain balance". The core of this theory is not to suppress emotions, but to restore the natural balance of human emotions and zang-fu organs through mutual restraint and dredging of emotions, which embodies the holistic view and syndrome differentiation view of TCM in emotional treatment.

1.2 Core Theoretical System of Five-Element Music

Five-element music, also known as five-tone therapy, is the core carrier of traditional TCM music therapy. It is constructed based on the TCM system of five elements, five zang-fu organs, and five emotions, and deeply integrates traditional musical tones with TCM visceral manifestation and emotional theories to form a systematic tone regulation and treatment system. Traditional five basic modes of tones include Jue, Zhi, Gong, Shang, and Yu, corresponding to wood, fire, earth, metal, and water five elements respectively. They further connect with the liver, heart, spleen, lung, kidney five zang-fu organs and anger, joy, thinking, sorrow, fear five emotions, constructing a four-in-one

TCM music regulation framework of "five tones – five elements – five zang-fu organs – five emotions".

Each mode of five-element music has unique tonal characteristics, rhythms, and qi regulation effects, adapting to different zang-fu functions and emotional states. Jue tone (wood mode) features melodious and slow rhythms, enters the liver meridian, soothes the liver and regulates qi, relieves stagnation, and improves emotional disorders such as liver qi stagnation, irritability and depression. Zhi tone (fire mode) is bright, vigorous and brisk, enters the heart meridian, boosts heart yang and smoothes heart qi, and ameliorates insufficient heart qi, low mood and listlessness. Gong tone (earth mode) is calm, profound and gentle, enters the spleen meridian, invigorates the spleen and harmonizes the middle jiao, regulates qi movement, and treats excessive thinking, qi stagnation and restlessness. Shang tone (metal mode) is clear, high-pitched and regular, enters the lung meridian, descends lung qi and converges qi movement, relieves lung qi stagnation, irritability and tantrum. Yu tone (water mode) is soft, calm and distant, enters the kidney meridian, nourishes kidney essence and calms the mind, and improves kidney qi deficiency, panic and mental restlessness.

The core mechanism of five-element music is to intervene the ascent, descent, exit and entry of human zang-fu qi movement through sound wave vibration of specific tones, regulate zang-fu qi and blood circulation, so as to dredge biased emotions and stabilize abnormal moods. Compared with conventional psychological intervention, five-element music realizes the precise correspondence of tones, zang-fu organs and emotions based on the TCM five-element system, and has the unique advantages of regulating both physique and spirit as well as treating body and mind simultaneously, serving as an important non-pharmacological emotional intervention method in TCM.

1.3 Compatibility Mechanism of the Two Theories

The therapeutic principle of "treating emotion with emotion" and five-element music therapy are not independent. They are highly consistent in theoretical connotation, action mechanism and therapeutic goals, forming a complete adaptation system of "theoretical guidance and carrier implementation", which provides core theoretical support for emotion-differentiated music application and precise emotional regulation. Traditional five-element music application mainly focuses on zang-fu syndrome differentiation, selects corresponding music modes according to zang-fu deficiency and excess, focuses on regulating zang-fu qi movement and tonifying zang-fu deficiency, but ignores the core pathogenesis of emotional imbalance, resulting in the limitation of "regulating zang-fu organs rather than emotions and treating symptoms rather than root causes". The integration of the "treating emotion with emotion" theory makes up for the shortcomings of the traditional music selection model, shifting five-element music from "regulating zang-fu organs" to "regulating emotions" and realizing targeted and precise emotional intervention.

In terms of theoretical connotation, both take the TCM five-element generation and restraint law as the

core underlying logic. The "treating emotion with emotion" theory restrains abnormal emotions relying on the law of five-emotion mutual restraint, while five-element music regulates corresponding emotions based on the five-element attributes of five tones. The two theories share the same origin and logical unity. The tonal characteristics of five tones can accurately match the imbalance state of five emotions, induce human body to produce corresponding peaceful emotions through tonal stimulation, and restrain excessive abnormal emotions via the emotional restraint principle, forming a complete action chain of "tonal stimulation, emotional harmonization, bias correction, and zang-fu stabilization". For example, excessive sorrow and lung qi stagnation can be treated with bright and relaxed Zhi tone based on the principle of "joy restrains sorrow", which stimulates joyful emotions, restrains sorrow and stagnation, smoothes heart and lung qi movement, and achieves dual regulation of emotions and zang-fu organs.

In terms of therapeutic goals, both follow the TCM treatment concept of "holistic harmonization and balancing for homeostasis", aiming to restore the unity of human physique and spirit by harmonizing emotions and smoothing qi movement rather than simply eliminating symptoms. The "treating emotion with emotion" theory provides a definite syndrome differentiation and emotional restraint principle for five-element music, solving the problems of ambiguous music selection basis and unguided music application. Five-element music provides a visualized and operable intervention carrier for the "treating emotion with emotion" theory, breaking the limitations of strong subjectivity, difficult implementation and poor standardization of traditional emotional therapy. Complementary and highly compatible, the two theories jointly construct a new five-element music application system of "emotion differentiation as the core, restraint as the basis, and five tones as the carrier", laying a solid theoretical foundation for the subsequent construction of music selection logic and emotion-differentiated music application model.

II. Construction of Five-Element Music Selection Logic Based on "Treating Emotion with Emotion"

2.1 Advantages and Disadvantages of Traditional Five-Element Music Selection Mode

Rooted in the basic theory of "five tones corresponding to five zang-fu organs", the traditional five-element music selection mode is the mainstream paradigm for the long-term clinical application of five-tone therapy. Its core logic is "zang-fu correspondence and music selection for organ diseases", that is, matching corresponding five-element music modes according to the deficiency, excess and prosperity of patients' zang-fu qi movement. For instance, Jue tone is mostly selected for liver dysfunction, Zhi tone for heart malnutrition, and Gong tone for spleen dysfunction. This mode constructs the basic framework for five-tone application, integrates tonal therapy with TCM visceral manifestation theory, eliminates the randomness of music selection merely based on auditory preference, and endows five-element music therapy with preliminary TCM theoretical basis. It has stable application value in

regulating zang-fu qi movement, relieving physical discomfort and assisting the recovery of zang-fu functions, laying a foundation for the inheritance and popularization of five-tone therapy.

However, with the increasing clinical demand for the intervention of emotional diseases, the limitations of the traditional zang-fu-oriented music selection mode have become prominent, failing to meet the clinical needs of precise emotional regulation. Firstly, traditional music selection prioritizes zang-fu organs over emotions, focusing on the regulation of organic and functional disorders of zang-fu organs while ignoring clinical scenarios with emotional imbalance as the core pathogenesis. Most emotional disorders caused by excessive or stagnant emotions are not accompanied by obvious zang-fu deficiency, so simple zang-fu corresponding music selection cannot target the root cause, easily leading to the intervention deviation of "regulating organs rather than emotions". Secondly, the music selection logic is single and rigid, lacking restraint thinking. Traditional music selection mostly adopts the "homologous tonification" strategy, which nourishes corresponding zang-fu organs with matching tones, only having the effect of strengthening vital qi and tonification without the function of restraint and bias correction, and cannot solve excess problems such as excessive emotions and qi stagnation. Thirdly, it lacks individualization and pertinence. Faced with complex emotional disorders such as mixed emotions and deficiency-excess intermingled emotional diseases prevalent in clinic, the traditional single corresponding music selection mode lacks flexible compatibility logic, resulting in mechanized and homogenized music selection schemes, failing to realize precise intervention and restricting the clinical efficacy and standardized promotion of five-element music therapy.

2.2 Core Music Selection Principles Guided by "Treating Emotion with Emotion"

Traditional five-element music selection is rooted in the theory of "five tones matching five zang-fu organs", serving as the mainstream application paradigm of five-tone therapy. Its core rule of "zang-fu correspondence and organ-based music selection" selects music modes according to patients' zang-fu deficiency-excess and qi prosperity-decline. This framework integrates tonal therapy with TCM visceral manifestation theory, avoids subjective music selection based on personal preference, and provides basic theoretical support for clinical application. It has positive effects on regulating zang-fu qi movement and relieving physical symptoms, promoting the inheritance and development of five-tone therapy.

Nevertheless, the traditional mode cannot adapt to the precise intervention needs of modern emotional diseases due to inherent defects. It overemphasizes zang-fu physical lesions while neglecting emotional pathological changes, resulting in invalid intervention for pure emotional disorders without organic lesions. The single tonification-oriented logic lacks restraint and correction effects, making it ineffective for excessive emotional stagnation and qi stagnation. In addition, the homogenized and rigid music selection scheme cannot cope with complex mixed emotional diseases, lacking

individualized and targeted intervention strategies, which severely limits the clinical popularization and efficacy improvement of five-element music therapy.

2.5 Refined Music Selection Logic for Five-Emotion Imbalance

Based on the five-emotion restraint law of "treating emotion with emotion", combined with the pathogenesis characteristics and tonal adaptation attributes of five basic emotional imbalances, this study constructs a refined and standardized five-emotion imbalance music selection system, clarifying the primary and auxiliary tones and selection basis for various emotional biases, and forming a one-to-one precise music selection logic.

Music selection logic for excessive thinking (thinking injures the spleen). Excessive thinking and qi stagnation are common clinical emotional imbalances corresponding to excessive earth element, often accompanied by restlessness, insomnia, dreaminess and abdominal distension. Following the therapeutic principle of "anger restrains thinking", wood-attributed Jue tone is selected as the primary music. With melodious and soothing characteristics, Jue tone can dredge stagnant spleen earth, smooth qi movement, eliminate qi stagnation caused by overthinking and restrain excessive thinking. For deficiency-excess intermingled conditions of long-term thinking-induced spleen injury and spleen qi deficiency, mild and profound Gong tone is matched as auxiliary music to invigorate the spleen, harmonize the middle jiao and strengthen vital qi, realizing the combination of stagnation dredging and vital qi tonification.

Music selection logic for excessive joy (joy dissipates heart qi). Excessive joy leads to scattered heart qi and hyperactive fire element, manifested as mental restlessness, emotional excitement, insomnia and palpitations. In accordance with the principle of "fear restrains joy", water-attributed Yu tone is taken as the primary music. With calm and low tones, Yu tone converges scattered heart qi, restrains hyperactive fire and calms excessive joyful emotions. For patients with consumed heart qi and deficient heart spirit, mild Zhi tone is used as auxiliary music to nourish heart qi and soothe the mind, preventing excessive restraint and heart qi injury.

Music selection logic for excessive sorrow (sorrow injures the lung). Excessive sorrow and lung qi stagnation correspond to excessive metal element, characterized by low mood, pessimism, chest tightness and disordered lung qi descent. Following the rule of "joy restrains sorrow", fire-attributed Zhi tone is selected as the primary music. Bright and uplifting Zhi tone stimulates joyful emotions, dispels sorrow and stagnation, and unblocks stagnant lung qi. For patients with deficient lung qi and listlessness caused by prolonged sorrow, clear and gentle Shang tone is matched as auxiliary music to descend lung qi, consolidate lung qi and regulate fundamental zang-fu deficiency.

Music selection logic for panic and fear (fear injures the kidney). Sudden or prolonged fear injures the kidney, leading to excessive water element, timidity, palpitation, insomnia and unconsolidated kidney qi. Based on the principle of "thinking restrains fear", earth-attributed Gong tone is adopted as the primary

music. Stable and profound Gong tone calms the mind, consolidates kidney qi, restrains floating fearful emotions and regulates disordered lower jiao water qi. For patients with deficient kidney essence and restless mind, soft Yu tone is used as auxiliary music to nourish kidney essence, soothe the mind and consolidate the root.

Music selection logic for irritability and anger (anger injures the liver). Liver qi stagnation and excessive anger are high-incidence clinical emotional disorders corresponding to hyperactive wood element, manifested as irritability, anxiety, hypochondriac distension and upward adverse qi movement. In accordance with the principle of "sorrow restrains anger", metal-attributed Shang tone is selected as the primary music. Clear and convergent Shang tone descends adverse liver qi, restrains hyperactive liver yang and suppresses excessive anger. For patients with liver stagnation and blood deficiency, melodious Jue tone is matched as auxiliary music to soothe the liver qi, harmonize liver blood, and regulate liver qi movement through combination of convergence and dredging.

III. Construction and Operation Specifications of Emotion-Differentiated Music Application Model

3.1 Construction Ideas and Objectives of the Model

Current clinical application of five-element music therapy generally has problems such as ambiguous music application standards, missing syndrome differentiation links, subjective music selection and inconsistent intervention procedures. Most music application methods remain at the level of empirical music matching and single zang-fu corresponding application, failing to give full play to the core advantage of emotional restraint of "treating emotion with emotion", resulting in uneven clinical intervention effects and hindering the formation of standardized and replicable music application systems. Based on the above constructed emotion-restricting music selection logic, combined with TCM emotional syndrome differentiation thinking and modern standardized non-pharmacological intervention concepts, this study constructs a closed-loop emotion-differentiated music application model characterized by "emotion differentiation as the core, five-element restraint as the criterion, standardized music application as the carrier, and dynamic balancing as the closed loop".

Breaking through the traditional single music application thinking of "prioritizing zang-fu organs over emotions", the model integrates emotional identification, pathogenesis judgment, music compatibility, standardized application and efficacy feedback, replacing the mechanized and homogenized traditional mode. Centering on the pathogenesis of five-emotion imbalance and guided by the five-emotion restraint law, it takes both fundamental zang-fu deficiency and superficial emotional excess into account, realizing precise emotional syndrome differentiation, targeted music compatibility, standardized application procedures and dynamic efficacy adjustment, and promoting the transformation of five-element music therapy from empirical application to theoretically guided and standardized practice.

The model has three core construction objectives. Theoretically, it improves the application system of the "treating emotion with emotion" theory in five-element music therapy, makes up for the theoretical deficiency of missing emotional syndrome differentiation in traditional music application, and enriches the theoretical connotation of TCM five-tone emotion regulation. Practically, it establishes a unified, standardized and operable emotion-differentiated music application process, solves the practical problems of random music selection, disordered application and chaotic compatibility, and improves the accuracy and effectiveness of five-element music intervention on emotional imbalance. In terms of popularization, it constructs a standardized intervention paradigm applicable to sub-health emotional disorders and mild-to-moderate emotional disturbances, providing a referential model for the standardized and popularized clinical application of TCM five-element music therapy.

3.2 Core Functional Modules of the Model

Combined with the pathogenesis characteristics of emotional diseases and the regulation rules of five-element music, the constructed emotion-differentiated music application model consists of four interconnected and closed-loop operating core modules, which cooperate progressively to form a complete emotional music intervention system.

First: Emotional Identification and Evaluation Module. As the premise and foundation of model operation, this module accurately judges the state of human emotional imbalance. Different from traditional zang-fu syndrome differentiation, it focuses on "emotion differentiation", combines TCM four diagnostic methods and emotional identification theories, distinguishes the biased types of anger, joy, thinking, sorrow and fear, differentiates single emotional imbalance and mixed complex emotions, and judges the deficiency-excess nature, severity and primary and secondary pathogenesis of emotional imbalance. Meanwhile, it combines zang-fu qi and blood status to clarify whether the emotional imbalance is a pure emotional disorder or secondary to zang-fu deficiency, providing core syndrome differentiation basis for precise music selection and targeted music application.

Second: Five-Tone Music Compatibility Module. As the core of the model, this module carries out tonal compatibility strictly following the four-dimensional emotion-restricting principles based on the results of emotional identification. Primary music is determined according to the five-emotion restraint law for excessive core emotions to realize the core effect of "restraining excessive emotions with moderate emotions". Auxiliary music is matched according to patients' zang-fu deficiency-excess and complicated emotional symptoms to harmonize zang-fu organs, strengthen vital qi and eliminate residual stagnation. The compatibility mode of "primary tone for restraint and auxiliary tone for consolidation" combines symptom correction and root regulation, solving the one-sidedness and limited efficacy of single-tone intervention.

Third: Standardized Music Application Execution Module. As the key carrier for model clinical implementation, this module standardizes the specific

clinical application schemes and operating specifications. It unifies the music application duration, listening frequency, scenario, state and cycle, and formulates differentiated schemes according to the characteristics of different emotional diseases. Hyperactive emotional disorders adopt short-duration and gentle music application to avoid excessive qi dissipation; stagnant emotional disorders appropriately extend the listening duration to gradually dredge qi stagnation. It also clarifies environmental and physical and mental state requirements during music application to avoid external interference and ensure therapeutic effects, eliminating the random and unstandardized traditional music listening mode.

Fourth: Efficacy Feedback and Optimization Module. As the guarantee for dynamic optimization and long-term stable operation of the model, this module forms a closed-loop intervention system. It evaluates the improvement of patients' emotional state, sleep quality, mood fluctuation and physical accompanying symptoms stage by stage to judge the adaptability of the current music scheme. If the core imbalanced emotion is significantly improved, the listening frequency and duration will be adjusted gradually to consolidate the curative effect; if the emotional improvement is unsatisfactory or emotional transformation and symptom changes occur, re-differentiation and tonal compatibility adjustment will be conducted, realizing the dynamic closed-loop of "application – evaluation – scheme adjustment – re-application" and ensuring individualized and adaptive intervention schemes.

3.3 Operation Process and Application Scope of the Model

The emotion-differentiated music application model follows a complete and standardized four-step closed-loop operation process: emotional identification and evaluation, precise music compatibility, standardized music application, and efficacy feedback and optimization. The progressive and interlocked process ensures high standardization and operability. Firstly, collect patients' emotional state, physical symptoms, sleep status and zang-fu pathogenesis information to clarify core imbalanced emotions and deficiency-excess pathogenesis. Secondly, formulate individualized music compatibility schemes with primary and auxiliary tones based on the five-emotion restraint law. Thirdly, implement standardized five-element music intervention in accordance with unified duration, frequency and scenarios. Fourthly, dynamically optimize the scheme according to emotional improvement until emotional balance and qi harmony are achieved, finally realizing holistic regulation of physique and spirit as well as yin-yang balance.

Compared with traditional modes, this model has clear operation logic and targeted syndrome differentiation, retaining the holistic regulation advantages of TCM while meeting the needs of modern clinical standardized intervention, and avoiding the drawbacks of empirical music application. It is applicable not only to simple single emotional imbalance for rapid emotional restraint, but also to complex diseases with mixed emotions and simultaneous zang-fu and emotional disorders, realizing precise intervention through primary and

secondary compatibility and dynamic scheme adjustment, adapting to diverse clinical emotional disease scenarios.

In terms of application scope, the model is suitable for various physical and mental disorders caused by emotional imbalance. Firstly, sub-health emotional disorders, including excessive thinking, sorrow stagnation, irritability, panic insomnia and other emotional abnormalities without organic lesions. Secondly, mild-to-moderate emotion-related physical and mental diseases, such as anxiety, depression, neurotic insomnia, liver depression and spleen deficiency, heart-spleen deficiency accompanied by emotional disorders. Thirdly, rehabilitation regulation of qi disorder after emotional stimulation, which can stabilize disordered emotions and harmonize zang-fu qi movement through standardized music intervention. Meanwhile, the model is not applicable to patients with severe mental disorders, serious organic lesions and those unable to cooperate with music intervention, clarifying the application boundary to ensure intervention safety and effectiveness.

IV. Model Application, Existing Problems and Research Prospects

4.1 Clinical Application of the Model in Emotional Diseases

Breaking through the limitation of single zang-fu regulation of traditional five-element music, the emotion-differentiated music application model constructed based on the "treating emotion with emotion" theory targets the core pathogenesis of emotional imbalance, and is highly applicable to most mild-to-moderate emotional disorders and emotion-related physical diseases. It realizes full standardized intervention of syndrome differentiation, music selection, application and scheme adjustment, with strong clinical practicability. The clinical application value of the model is reflected in the intervention of four typical high-incidence emotional diseases: liver depression and irritability, insomnia due to excessive thinking, sorrow and depression, panic and anxiety.

Liver depression and irritability syndrome. The core pathogenesis is hyperactive liver wood and upward adverse qi movement with excessive anger, accompanied by irritability, hypochondriac distension, emotional restlessness and insomnia. Guided by the principle of "sorrow restrains anger", the model identifies excessive anger as the core imbalance, selecting metal-attributed Shang tone as the primary music to converge hyperactive liver yang, descend adverse liver qi and restrain excessive anger. Combined with long-term liver stagnation and qi stagnation, wood-attributed Jue tone is matched as auxiliary music to soothe liver qi and dredge stagnation, avoiding qi stagnation caused by single convergence intervention. Standardized quiet and fixed-time listening is adopted to smooth qi movement, and the scheme is adjusted dynamically according to symptom improvement, achieving synergistic effects of anger restraint, liver soothing and qi regulation.

Insomnia syndrome due to excessive thinking. Caused by excessive thinking, spleen earth stagnation and qi stagnation with excessive thinking as the core pathogenesis, it is manifested as persistent overthink-

ing, mental tension, difficulty falling asleep, dream-disturbed sleep and lassitude. After identifying excessive thinking via syndrome differentiation, the model selects melodious Jue tone as the primary music based on the principle of "anger restrains thinking" to eliminate spleen-stomach qi stagnation and relieve excessive thinking. For deficiency-excess intermingled symptoms of long-term thinking-induced spleen injury and insufficient qi and blood, profound Gong tone is matched as auxiliary music to invigorate the spleen, tonify qi and blood, and realize simultaneous treatment of symptoms and root causes. The closed-loop intervention continuously dredges qi stagnation and relieves mental tension, improving insomnia and physical discomfort caused by excessive thinking.

Sorrow and depression syndrome. Characterized by excessive metal element and stagnant sorrow, it presents as low mood, pessimism, chest tightness and lassitude, common in sub-health depressive mood and mild depression. Following the principle of "joy restrains sorrow", the model selects uplifting Zhi tone as the primary music to stimulate joyful emotions, boost depressed heart qi, unblock stagnant lung qi and restrain sorrow bias. For patients with prolonged illness, deficient qi and listlessness, mild Gong tone is matched to strengthen vital qi and soothe the mind, harmonizing zang-fu qi movement. Standardized cyclic music application gradually eliminates emotional stagnation, boosts physical and mental state, and relieves low mood.

Panic and anxiety syndrome. Caused by excessive kidney water and unstable fear emotion, with the core pathogenesis of unconsolidated kidney qi and restless mind, it is manifested as timidity, palpitations, restlessness and night terrors. Based on the principle of "thinking restrains fear", the model selects stable Gong tone as the primary music to calm the mind, consolidate kidney qi and restrain floating fear. Soft Yu tone is matched as auxiliary music to nourish kidney essence, soothe the mind and consolidate the root, improving the fundamental deficiency of kidney qi and reducing recurrent panic and anxiety, realizing the intervention effects of calming the mind, stabilizing will and harmonizing heart and kidney.

4.2 Existing Problems of Current Five-Element Music Application

Despite the unique advantages of five-element music therapy in emotional and zang-fu regulation and the optimization effect of the constructed model, the clinical application and academic research of five-element music still have many urgent problems restricting its standardization, normalization and popularization.

First, the lack of specialized emotional syndrome differentiation system leads to ambiguous music selection basis. Most current clinical schemes adhere to the traditional "five tones matching five zang-fu organs" mode, prioritizing zang-fu organs over emotions and lacking targeted emotional syndrome differentiation. Music selection is mostly based on physical zang-fu symptoms rather than core emotional imbalance types, deficiency-excess attributes and mixed symptoms, ignoring the "treating emotion with emotion" principle,

often resulting in the dilemma of "correct organ matching but ineffective emotional intervention", with unstable intervention efficacy due to insufficient pathogenesis basis.

Second, homogenized music schemes lack individualized compatibility. Current clinical application adopts fixed single-tone schemes with unified duration, without individualized adjustment according to patients' age, constitution, emotional imbalance degree and mixed emotional symptoms. Single-tone intervention cannot balance the primary and secondary pathogenesis of complex mixed emotional disorders and deficiency-excess intermingled diseases, and lacks the "primary and auxiliary tone compatibility" thinking, failing to realize precise and individualized intervention for complex clinical scenarios.

Third, non-standardized operation lacks unified execution criteria. There is no unified industry standard for the duration, frequency, time period and environment of five-element music intervention. Many applications adopt random background music listening without standardized intervention cycles and physical and mental state requirements, greatly reducing the therapeutic effect. The inconsistent operation standards lead to poor efficacy repeatability and comparability among different studies, seriously restricting clinical popularization.

Fourth, single efficacy evaluation lacks dynamic closed-loop regulation. Current intervention evaluation mostly relies on single emotional scales or physical symptom improvement, ignoring the holistic TCM regulation effects on emotions, zang-fu organs and qi movement with one-sided evaluation indicators. Most interventions are unidirectional without phased efficacy feedback and dynamic scheme adjustment mechanisms, failing to adapt to the mutable characteristics of emotional pathogenesis, resulting in limited long-term efficacy.

Fifth, disconnection between theoretical research and clinical application leads to insufficient application of the "treating emotion with emotion" theory. Most existing studies only borrow the basic five-element framework of five tones, without in-depth application of the core emotional restraint mechanism. Most interventions stay at the superficial level of regulating zang-fu organs and qi movement, failing to realize the core therapeutic value of "restraining emotions with emotions and correcting imbalance", resulting in insufficient excavation of the emotional intervention advantages of five-element music and mismatched theoretical and clinical value.

V. Research Limitations and Future Prospects

Based on the core "treating emotion with emotion" theory in *Huangdi Neijing*, this study systematically sorts out the compatibility mechanism between five-element music and emotional restraint, reconstructs traditional music selection logic, and constructs a standardized closed-loop emotion-differentiated music intervention model. It effectively compensates for the traditional shortcomings of prioritizing organs over emotions, random music application and unstable efficacy, improves the theoretical system of TCM five-tone emotion regulation, and provides innovative theoretical

ideas and practical paradigms for non-pharmacological precise intervention of emotional imbalance diseases.

This study still has certain limitations. First, it focuses on theoretical deduction and model construction, lacking evidence from large-sample and multi-center clinical trials, and the clinical efficacy and applicable boundary of the model need further quantitative verification. Second, the differentiation of complex mixed emotional pathogenesis, the weight of multi-tone compatibility and hierarchical application standards are not refined enough, resulting in room for improvement in the intervention accuracy of complex diseases. Third, the efficacy evaluation relies mainly on subjective symptoms, lacking modern objective physiological indicators to verify the microcosmic mechanism and material basis of the therapy. Fourth, the individualized intervention dimension is limited, without refined special schemes for different populations such as the elderly and adolescents.

Future research can be deepened and optimized from four dimensions: theoretical refinement, empirical verification, technical empowerment and standard normalization. First, further explore ancient medical literature and clinical experience to refine the syndrome differentiation criteria of single and mixed emotional imbalance, and standardize tone compatibility and application procedures to improve the theoretical rigor of the model. Second, carry out high-quality randomized controlled trials to quantitatively compare the efficacy differences between this model and traditional modes, providing high-level evidence-based medical support for clinical promotion. Third, construct a multi-dimensional efficacy evaluation system combining subjective emotional scales and objective physiological indicators such as electroencephalogram and neurotransmitters to clarify the microcosmic mechanism of five-element music therapy. Fourth, build an intelligent emotion-differentiated music application system based on artificial intelligence and big data to realize automatic syndrome differentiation and personalized intelligent music matching, and refine hierarchical intervention schemes for different groups. Fifth, unify industry operation standards, explore combined intervention

modes with traditional Chinese medicine, acupuncture and psychological counseling, expand the clinical application scenarios of five-element music, and promote the standardized, intelligent and popularized inheritance and innovation of TCM non-pharmacological therapies.

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